

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF CAPPARIS SPINOSE PLANT

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As a result of radical reforms in the cultivation of medicinal plants, one of the leading sectors of the pharmaceutical industry in the country, the number of medicinal plants is growing year by year and the introduction of medicinal plants is developing to meet the demand for raw materials in the pharmaceutical industry.

The capparidaceae belongs to the Capparidaceae family and is a perennial liana-like herbaceous plant with thorny thorns up to 2.5 m tall. The leaves are round, inverted ovate or elliptical, arranged in a series on the stems and branches using a band. The white, large four-lobed flowers are located in the leaf axils with a long band. The fruit is multi-seeded, inverted ovoid, juicy, resembling a wet fruit. capparidaceae blooms in May-June, the fruits ripen in July-August. Experts associate the origin of this name with the Kavir Desert in the Iranian steppe. Because buckthorn is the most common plant in this area. It is cultivated in France, Spain, Italy, Algeria and in Cyprus, Greece and North America. There are 150 species of prickly pears, 2 of which grow in Uzbekistan (*S.spinosa*, *S.rosanoviana*). It grows naturally on the mountain slopes of our country. This thorny shrub, which grows well in the ground, does not choose a place, resistant to drought and frost. It grows from May to October. The capparidaceae is a medicinal plant from root to leaf. It is also a nutritious food for livestock.

Barbed wire is also valued as a valuable raw material in the pharmaceutical and food industries.

In folk medicine it is used on the surface, fruit and root of the capparidaceae. The topsoil is collected when the plant is in bloom and the shade is dried on the ground.

The flower is harvested when the plant is in full bloom and the fruit is ripe. The flower is dried in the shade and the fruit in the open air in the sun.

Capparidaceae root is dug in early spring or late autumn. It is washed in water, cleaned of soil and dried in the sun.

The most useful part is the bark of the root.

Properties

It is absorbent, opening and cleansing. The root is disintegrating, softening, cleansing and opening. Its bark has the properties of bitterness, sharpness and

wrinkle. The fruit is especially nutritious when salted. Freshly picked fruit contains more nutrients than dried prickly pear fruit.

All parts of the pumpkin plant contain useful substances, which are: rutin, quercetin C (ascorbic acid), vitamin, stachidrin, thioglycosides, saponins, dyes, fruit-sugar, vitamin flavonoids, thioglycosides; oil in the seeds; alkaloids in the root (staxidrin, caparidin); contains flavonoids, sugars, coumarins and other active biological substances.

Use in medicine.

Swelling and rash.

The root swells and absorbs hard tumors. The root is mixed with something that breaks the (harmful) force, the leaf is a drug tested in this respect.

Injuries and wounds.

The bark of the root is of great benefit when placed on ugly wounds of poor quality.

Joints of human.

The bark of the root is useful for rashes and side pains, sometimes it is very useful when swallowed with sap from the scalp, it is also useful for paralysis and coagulation, it strengthens the limbs due to its wrinkles. It is therefore very useful for meat breaks that occur in the head and middle of the muscles.

The brain organs.

Chewing the bark of the root absorbs moisture from the head and relieves cold pain in the head. Its juice is instilled against the worms in the ear. It is necessary to chew the bark of the root, especially on the cheek or leaf, against toothache.

Respiratory and thoracic organs.

Cap.Spinosa salting is recommended for patients with asthma.

Nutritional organs

The bark itself is very useful, especially when the bark of the root is drunk in spleen disease, and when the spleen hardens, either barley, or a powder of something like barley, thickly greased with flour. Often the spleen is emptied of the thick commercial substance, resulting in the spleen healing.

The excretory organ.

Raw, rubs the thick mucus, circulates menstrual blood, kills ions and vomiting in the intestines. Beneficial for hemorrhoids, if it is consumed salted before meals, it sucks the stomach.

Agrotechnics and its importance in agriculture.

The Capparis spinosa bush grows naturally mainly in mountainous and hilly areas. Nowadays, it is grown in greenhouses.

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